

Interaction between Polybasic Acids and Neutral Salts. Part I. *ortho*-Phosphoric Acid.

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The dissociation constants of *ortho*-phosphoric acid, determined by different methods differ considerably (Abbot and Bray, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **31**, 729 ; Michaelis and Garmedia, *Biochem. Z.*, 1914, **67**, 413 ; Michaelis and Krüger, *Biochem. Z.*, 1921, **119**, 307 ; Prideaux and Ward, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **125**, 423 ; Noyes and Sherrill, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 1861 ; Kolthoff, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1927, **46**, 350).

In the present paper the activities of the hydrogen ion determined from measurements of electromotive force in mixtures of phosphoric acid with chloride, bromide and iodide of potassium are recorded. In some instances measurements with Thymol Blue have been made using a Helige Immersion Colorimeter.

The thermodynamic dissociation constant K of a monobasic acid, defined by the equation

$$K = \frac{a_+ a_-}{a_1}, \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

should be independent of the concentration of the acid, provided the same solvent is used; a_+ , a_- and a_1 are respectively the activities of the hydrogen ion, anion and the neutral molecule.

In *dilute* solutions of neutral salt, it is generally assumed that the thermodynamic dissociation constant is constant and independent of the nature of the salt. It is also sometimes assumed that the activity coefficient of the undissociated molecule is independent of the ionic strength and is taken to be unity (Larsson, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, **155**, 247 ; Noyes and Sherrill, *loc. cit.*; McInnes, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 2068; Cohn, *ibid.*, 1927, **49**, 173). We have thus

$$K = \frac{\gamma_H C_H \gamma_A C_A}{C_{HA}} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The first dissociation constant of phosphoric acid is moderately strong. At concentrations above $\cdot 001M$ it can be treated as a monobasic acid and C_H and $C_{H_2PO_4}$ can be taken to be identical without sensible error. Hence we get

$$K_1 = \frac{a^2_H}{C_{H_3PO_4}} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

It would appear from the following data that at near about normal concentrations of the halides, there is a sudden increase in the activity.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A Leeds and Northrup K-type potentiometer was used. A Dolezalek-type hydrogen electrode vessel, made of borosilicate glass with ground stopper, was employed (Mukherjee and Kumar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2179). Merck's pure phosphoric acid (d , 1.7) was made into a stock solution and the strength determined gravimetrically. A few drops of toluol were added to it. The salts employed were of Merck's Reagent quality. The concentrations are given in gm. molecules per 1000 gm. of water. A saturated KCl bridge was used. A second vessel containing the solution was interposed between the hydrogen electrode and the salt bridge and connected with the latter by an inverted U-shaped syphon tube. The lower portion of the syphon tube was used to effect connection between the salt bridge and solution and the vertical limb was closed. The thermostat was maintained at 35° . The electromotive force of the calomel vessel was measured against 0.1N-HCl with identical arrangement and this was found to be 0.3492 volt. The activity coefficient of .1N-HCl at 35° was taken to be .7956 (Mukherjee and Kumar, *loc. cit.*). Reduction of phosphoric acid by hydrogen in presence of platinum does not appear to take place as the electromotive force remains constant over fairly long periods (3 hours) and is generally reproducible.

TABLE I.

Conc. of salt (M).	E.M.F. (Corrected)	p_{H}	
		Electrometric.	Colorimetric.
0	0.3975	1.90	1.96
.01 KCl	0.3975	1.90	1.99
.1	0.3975	1.90	1.98
1.032	0.3920	1.81	—
.01 KBr	0.3972	1.90	1.96
.1	0.3963	1.88	1.97
1.040	0.3888	1.76	1.78
.01 KI	0.3972	1.90	1.96
.1	0.3963	1.88	1.97
1.051*	0.3981	1.77	—

TABLE II.

Conc. of salt (M).	E. M. F. (Corrected)	p_{H}	
		Electrometric.	Colorimetric.
0	.4424	2.64	2.7
.01 KCl	.4422	2.64	2.7
.1	.4424	2.64	2.7
1.033	.4386	2.58	2.59
.01 KBr	.4408	2.61	2.63
.1	.4408	2.61	2.61
1.040	.4360	2.53	2.59
.01 KI	.4412	2.62	2.65
.1	.4418	2.63	2.66
1.051*	.4400	2.60	—

* At this concentration free iodine is liberated; on continued passage of hydrogen, HI is formed and the colour is discharged.

TABLE III.

 $\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 = 0.033 \text{ M.}$

Conc. of salt (M).	a_{H} (exp.) $\times 10^2$	γ	$C_{\text{H}} =$ $\frac{a_{\text{H}}}{\gamma}$	$C_{\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4}$ $= C - C_{\text{H}}$	$K_1 =$ $\frac{a_{\text{H}}^2 \text{ (exp.)}}{C_{\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4}}$	$K'_1 =$ $\frac{a_{\text{H}}^2 \text{ (exp.)}}{C}$
0	1.26	.850	1.48×10^{-2}	1.85×10^{-2}	8.58×10^{-3}	4.77×10^{-3}
.01 KCl	1.26	.831	1.51×10^{-2}	1.82×10^{-2}	8.72×10^{-3}	4.77×10^{-3}
.1	1.26	.782	1.61×10^{-2}	1.72×10^{-2}	9.23×10^{-3}	4.77×10^{-3}
1.03	1.55	.708	2.19×10^{-2}	1.14×10^{-2}	2.10×10^{-2}	7.21×10^{-3}
.01 KBr	1.26	.831	1.51×10^{-2}	1.82×10^{-2}	8.72×10^{-3}	4.77×10^{-3}
.1	1.32	.782	1.69×10^{-2}	1.64×10^{-2}	1.06×10^{-2}	5.23×10^{-3}
1.04	1.74	.707	2.46×10^{-2}	8.7×10^{-3}	3.48×10^{-2}	9.09×10^{-3}
.01 KI	1.26	.834	1.51×10^{-2}	1.82×10^{-2}	8.72×10^{-3}	4.77×10^{-3}
.1	1.32	.782	1.69×10^{-2}	1.64×10^{-2}	1.06×10^{-2}	5.23×10^{-3}
1.05	1.70	.707	2.40×10^{-2}	9.3×10^{-3}	3.10×10^{-2}	8.68×10^{-3}

TABLE IV.

 $\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4 = 0.0033 \text{ M.}$

Conc. of salt (M.)	a_{H} (exp.) $\times 10^3$	γ	$C_{\text{H}} =$ $\frac{a_{\text{H}}}{\gamma}$	$C_{\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4}$ $= C - C_{\text{H}}$	$K_1 =$ $\frac{a_{\text{H}}^2 \text{ (exp.)}}{C_{\text{H}_3\text{PO}_4}}$	$K'_1 =$ $\frac{a_{\text{H}}^2 \text{ (exp.)}}{C}$
0	2.29	.941	2.43×10^{-3}	9.0×10^{-4}	5.82×10^{-3}	1.57×10^{-3}
.01 KCl	2.29	.892	2.56×10^{-3}	7.7×10^{-4}	6.81×10^{-3}	1.57×10^{-3}
.1	2.29	.779	2.94×10^{-3}	3.9×10^{-4}	1.34×10^{-2}	1.57×10^{-3}
1.03	2.63	.705	3.73×10^{-3}	—	—	2.08×10^{-3}
.01 KBr	2.45	.892	2.74×10^{-3}	5.9×10^{-4}	1.01×10^{-2}	1.80×10^{-3}
.1	2.45	.779	3.14×10^{-3}	1.9×10^{-4}	3.16×10^{-2}	1.80×10^{-3}
.104	2.95	.703	4.19×10^{-3}	—	—	2.61×10^{-3}
.01 KI	2.40	.892	2.69×10^{-3}	6.4×10^{-4}	9.00×10^{-3}	1.73×10^{-2}
.1	2.34	.779	3.00×10^{-3}	3.3×10^{-4}	1.66×10^{-2}	1.64×10^{-3}
1.05	2.51	.703	3.57×10^{-3}	—	—	1.89×10^{-3}

The concentration of the undissociated phosphoric acid has been calculated as follows: Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*) obtained value of K_1 ranging between 8.5 and 9.5×10^{-3} between the concentrations $.001 M$ and $.1M$. a_H can be calculated from the following equation using the mean value:—

$$a_H = - \frac{K_1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{K_1^2 + 4 K_1 C} \quad \dots (4)$$

where C , is the concentration of the acid. Assuming as a first approximation that the activity coefficient is unity, a_H as determined above can be put as C_H and this value can be subsequently used in calculating the ionic strength of the ions formed from of the acid. The activity coefficient is then obtained from Harned's formula (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 326), assuming that the mean activity coefficient of ions formed by the first dissociation of phosphoric acid is the same as that for HCl of corresponding mixtures.

The concentration of hydrogen ion is obtained by dividing the activity of hydrogen ion by the activity coefficient so found. Evidently it is being assumed that HCl is completely dissociated at these concentrations, for in calculating activity coefficient, the total concentration is used. The concentration of undissociated phosphoric acid is obtained by difference, assuming that the other stages of dissociation occur in negligible amounts.

Discussion.

The error in the value of K_1 arising out of the uncertainties of the liquid—junction potential does not appear to be great. The values obtained for the more concentrated acid solutions at lower concentrations of salt are in substantial agreement with those obtained by Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*). The low value for the more dilute acid solutions observed in the absence of the neutral salt may be ascribed in part to the errors of measurement of hydrogen-ion activity at such concentrations. The relative variation in the activity is much less subject to the errors arising out of uncertainties of the liquid—junction potential. It is rather striking that the activity remains constant up to $.1N$ salt solution, although the ionic strength changes about 3 times. The increase of K'_1 with ionic strength is to be referred to the constancy of the activity and the method of calculation.

On the other hand, using total concentrations as in K'_1 , the constant is found to be fairly independent of the salt concentration up to $\cdot 1N$. The inconstancy of K_1 can scarcely be accounted for from considerations of changes of the activity coefficients of the undissociated molecules, for it would require variation of the activity coefficient of the neutral molecule by several hundred per cent. It cannot also be accounted for by considerations of changes in the junction potential. It is difficult to believe that variation in the junction potential will exactly balance the changes in the activity. The constancy in the observed activity requires an explanation. Moreover the activities for the two dilutions of the acid are in a constant ratio up to $\cdot 1 N$ salt concentration. The ratio of the activities for the two concentrations of the acid and at the same concentration of a salt is practically constant, when the concentration of the latter does not exceed $\cdot 1 N$. But it decreases in the order $Cl > Br > I$ for the normal concentration (1.83, 1.76, 1.46).

It would thus appear that specific effects are at work. Broadly speaking, the results point to the conclusion that each of these salt-solutions should be treated as a separate solvent. At very low ionic strengths, the solutions can be treated as being identical and the limiting dissociation constant would appear to be about 8.5×10^{-3} . On passing from $\cdot 1 N$ to $1.0 N$ concentration, the change in the value of the constant is remarkable; it increases five times in some cases. Apart from a recognition of the specific solvent properties of each salt concentration, reference may be made to two other possible reasons for these variations. These are as follows:—

(i) The activity coefficients used in calculating the concentrations of the undissociated acid and the method of calculation itself are not valid. It is difficult however to account for the wide variations from such considerations.

(ii) The other possibility is that the activity of the hydrogen ions is not equal to that of the univalent $H_2PO_4^-$ ions. This inequality may arise from a difference in their concentrations. The second and third dissociation constants of phosphoric acid are given by Prideaux and Ward (*loc. cit.*) to be equal to 6×10^{-8} and 1.1×10^{-12} respectively and as has been stated before, these stages of dissociation may be neglected. The possibility remains however that certain amount of anions containing potassium may be formed. This would have the effect of lowering the concentration of $H_2PO_4^-$ ions. This would increase with the concentration of the salt.

Further experiments in the light of the above points are in progress.

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